

Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing For Mental Health Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Delving into the complexities of mental health issues has transformed into a dynamic exploration, seamlessly integrating the potency of databases and insightful questionnaires. Harnessing the capabilities of Large Language Models, we've crafted a perceptive chatbot that operates in tandem with our website, delivering responses akin to human interaction to user inquiries. Leveraging datasets sourced from Hugging Face pertaining to mental health, we've trained the LLM to generate tailored responses to users' queries, aiding in their mental health analysis. As we scrutinized existing models, we observed that the responses provided lacked depth and human-like nuance. To remedy this, we developed a chatbot designed to bridge this gap, offering more insightful solutions. Coupled with a questionnaire website that facilitates users in understanding their experiences, our chatbot, driven by LLM technology, assists users in navigating and coping with their mental health challenges.

Keywords: Large Language Model (LLM), Machine Learning (ML), Mental health, Advanced Algorithms, Mental health pattern.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental illnesses, also known as mental health disorders, are highly prevalent worldwide and represent one of the most serious public health concerns. There are many different types of mental illnesses, including depression, suicidal ideation, bipolar disorder, autism spectrum disorder (ASD), anxiety disorder, and schizophrenia. Each of these can negatively impact an individual's physical health and well-being, a problem exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the latest statistics, millions of people globally suffer from one or more mental disorders. Early detection of mental illness can significantly improve disease progression and treatment outcomes. Mental illness affects a person's emotions, thoughts, and social interactions, leading to serious consequences across different societies. These issues highlight the urgent need for new prevention and intervention strategies. To implement these strategies, early detection of mental illness is an essential procedure [1]. Mental disorders are usually diagnosed on the bases

of personal report, which requires questionnaires designed to identify specific emotional or social interaction patterns.[2] disorder [3]. The World Health Organization (WHO) provides an overview of the regional level of barriers to the diagnosis of various Cognitive problems and encourages people to acquire scientific knowledge to solve the problem of mental health. Today, thanks to the development of tech and bio medics, there are various techniques to check one's mental health. Research in the mental health has increased highly and this has resulted in knowledge about different parts of mental health that can be applied to various problems [4] There are many steps we use to diagnose mental health problems. a simple but effective way to diagnose users' mental health problems, which is a knowledge quiz or questionnaire, and it is a simple process that can be done quickly. Diagnosis usually begins with a special interview filled with questions about symptoms, medical history and physical examination. Using the research we read, we were able to create questions that would help analyze the user's

mental health and create a report. In addition, mental health problems can harm adults, especially their families, workplaces and society. There are many mental disorders commonly known as the inability to control fear or anxiety. Panic disorders, which appear to be sudden panic attacks and intense fear, fall into this category. Physiological symptoms caused by panic disorder include palpitations, sweating, and dizziness. Numbness caused by traumatic events is characteristic of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). People with social anxiety disorder are often afraid of social situations. Studies show that delay in seeking professional treatment for anxiety disorders is common [6]. The primary symptom of depression is a mood disorder, which is usually severe sadness. Sometimes the symptoms of depression can be dominated by anger, irritability and loss of interest. Regarding physiological symptoms, sleep disorders, appetite disturbances and decreased energy are common in different cultures. Patients may experience cognitive symptoms such as slow thinking, suicidal thoughts and feelings of guilt. [7]. We were able to create a questionnaire website by designing a user-friendly interface that prompts users with relevant questions about their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. These questions were carefully curated to encompass a broad spectrum of mental health indicators, allowing users to self-assess their well-being in a structured manner. Through the website, users can navigate through the questionnaire, inputting their responses confidentially. Once completed, the website processes the data and generates a summarized report outlining key insights and potential areas of concern regarding the user's mental health condition and send it to user's email. To connect this questionnaire functionality with the mental health chatbot, we integrated an application programming interface (API) that allows seamless communication between the two platforms. Upon completing the questionnaire, users are presented with the option to engage with the chatbot for further support and guidance based on their personalized results. This integration ensures a holistic approach to mental health support, empowering users to gain a deeper understanding of their mental well-being and access tailored assistance through both structured assessment and interactive dialogue.

II. LITERATURE WORK

We have explored a wide range of research paper giving us idea of ML/NLP approaches related to mental health

Conclusions from paper by Anu Priyaa, Shruti Garga and Neha Prerna Tigga they proposed machine learning model for predicting different levels of depression, anxiety and stress. They applied different machine learning algorithms like decision tree, random forest, naïve bayes, support vector machine and K-Nearest neighbour. They also calculated different comparison factors for choosing the best algorithm and found out that naïve bayes algorithm gives the best result.[9]

One from Astha Singh and Divya Kumar proposed a model for identification of anxiety and depression. They collected the data by using standard DASS-21 questionnaire. They used some of the standard machine learning algorithms like SVM, decision tree, random forest, naïve bayes and KNN for training and testing purpose. They got better accuracy for naïve bayes classifier among all other.[10]

Paper by G. Parimala,R. Kayalvizhi, S. Nithiya proposed a ML model for Mental Health: Detection & Diagnosis in which they detected whether a person is suffering from detection and tries to diagnosis We tested few ML algorithms depending upon our parameters that we would be further using to test our model. Thereby, the algorithm giving the best accuracy has been used.[11]

Saleh Afzoon, Nabi Rezvani, Farshad Khunjush explained that Mental health disorders are among the most important problems of recent decade as they have various Mental health issues can have significant individual and social impacts in their research paper. Organizational staff, including law enforcement and mental health department personnel, are as susceptible to mental health disorders as anyone else. Due to the critical nature of their roles, which are vital to the lives of citizens, they may be even more vulnerable to mental health challenges, making their work particularly overwhelming at times.[12]

Research paper by Reuben Crasto, Lance Dias, Dominic Miranda, and Deepali Kayande proposed a system designed to alleviate the problem by offering a chatbot to students, providing support similar to that of a counselor or therapist. Recent advancements in technology, particularly in machine learning, have shown significant effectiveness in aiding mental health recovery. This method includes surveys, questionnaires, data analysis, and natural language processing. The goal

is to create an online platform through which this tool will operate.[13]

Research by Vivek More, Viren Koli, Vignesh Vijaykumar, Vimal Jethani proposed a Chatbot for mental wellbeing build a therapy chatbot with a aim of providing a solution to the Mental health problem. A therapy chatbot will provide an easily accessible medium that will provide a hassle-free service to its user.[14]

Conclusions drawn by Vedant Vajre, Mitch Naylor, Udayamath and Amarda Shehu proposed an innovative mental health language model aimed at addressing mental health issues and presents several key contributions. Firstly, it introduces a classification system and provides an extensive dataset of social media text pertaining to mental health.[15]

Paper by Israt Jahan Dristy, Abdullah Matin Saad, Annajiat Alim Rasel proposed a paper on “Mental Health Status Prediction Using ML Classifiers with NLP Based Approaches” which provide the mental health status of the person by making use of ML classifiers and NLP approaches.[16]

Research by K Kroenke, R L Spitzer, J B Williams has focuses on improving the detection of depression, assessment of severity which is also important in guiding treatment decisions [17]

Robert L Spitzer, Kurt Kroenke, Janet B W Williams, Bernd Löwe Generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) is one of the most common mental disorders; however, there is no brief clinical measure for assessing GAD. The objective of their study was to develop a brief self-report scale to identify probable cases of GAD and evaluate its reliability and validity. And we did utilize it in our model.[18]

Conclusions from Ronald C Kessler 1, Lenard Adler, Minnie Ames, Olga Demler, Steve Faraone, Eva Hiripi, Mary J Howes, Robert Jin, Kristina Secnik, Thomas Spencer, T Bedirhan Ustun, Ellen E Walters ASRS includes 18 questions about frequency of recent DSM-IV Criterion A symptoms of adult ADHD. The ASRS screener consists of six out of these 18 questions that were selected based on stepwise logistic regression to optimize concordance with the clinical classification [19]

Annabel Prins, Michelle J. Bovin, Derek J. Smolenski, Brian P. Marx, Rachel Kimerling, concluded on objective of revising the Primary Care PTSD screen (PC-PTSD) to reflect the new Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) criteria for PTSD

(PC-PTSD-5) and to examine both the diagnostic accuracy and the patient acceptability of the revised measure.[20]

All of this led as to understand and build our own model to assess mental health of a person and create a chatbot to help the patient with human like answers to any question they have regarding there health or for emotional support.

III.METHODOLOGY

LLM, or Large Language Model, is an advanced type of artificial intelligence system designed to comprehend and produce text that resembles human language. These models undergo extensive training on massive datasets of written material, enabling them to grasp context, generate logical responses, and carry out tasks based on human language input. LLMs rely on sophisticated deep learning methods, particularly neural networks, to analyze and generate text, enabling them to handle a diverse range of language-related activities such as translation, summarization, question answering, and conversational dialogue. Notable examples of LLMs include GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) models created by OpenAI, which have garnered significant attention for their remarkable text generation abilities. LLMs find applications in various domains, including natural language comprehension, content creation, chatbots, and automated writing aids.

A. Which LLM we use to create our Chatbot?

We employ MelloGPT-AWQ, which utilizes an efficient, accurate, and exceptionally fast low-bit weight quantization approach. Currently accommodating 4-bit quantization compared to GPTQ, it delivers quicker transformer-based inference with comparable or superior quality compared to widely used GPTQ configurations. Our chatbot is built upon the MelloGPT base model, trained on custom datasets sourced from Hugging Face. These datasets comprise data scraped from the counsilchat.com forum, featuring expert responses provided by licensed clinicians to inquiries from various users.

B. Benefits of our chosen LLM

- 1) Mello-GPT uses a custom dataset to answer users query related to mental health
- 2) Mello-GPT has an improved language understanding and generation ability
- 3) Mello-GPT also has a higher fidelity and fewer errors in the field of medical query resolution
- 4) Mello-GPT has more efficient fine tuning
- 5) Mello-GPT works with a hybrid learning technique to achieve most optimal result.

C. Figma & Framer

Figma is a cloud-based design and prototyping tool used primarily by UI/UX designers for creating user interfaces, prototypes, and collaborative design projects. It offers a platform where multiple team members can work simultaneously on the same design project in real-time, facilitating seamless collaboration and version control. Figma provides a range of features including vector editing tools, prototyping capabilities, and design libraries, making it a versatile solution for both individual designers and design teams. Its web-based nature allows users to access and work on their designs from any device with an internet connection, enhancing flexibility and accessibility making it a popular choice among designers and design teams.

Framer is a prototyping and interactive design tool primarily used for creating high-fidelity prototypes and animations for web and mobile applications. It provides a platform where designers and developers can collaborate on the creation of interactive interfaces, animations, and user experiences. Framer offers a wide range of features including a powerful code editor, customizable design components, animation tools, and real-time previews, allowing users to create sophisticated and realistic prototypes that closely resemble the final product. One of the key features of Framer is its ability to integrate seamlessly with design and development workflows, enabling designers to import designs from tools like Sketch or Figma and developers to export code directly from prototypes. Framer is widely used by designers and design teams to prototype and iterate on user interfaces and interactions, making it a valuable tool in the product design process.

D. How we use Framer to successfully deploy a working website?

After Creating our UI design in Figma with the help of plugins we were able to duplicate the UI design onto framer then, we were able to added and rearrange the design as per our requirement and animation redirecting links other plugins and successfully deploy our website.

E. Questionaries

After successfully developing our website using Framer, our next step was to implement a questionnaire feature to enable users to assess their mental health. To facilitate this, we created sets of questions targeting various mental health disorders and issues, including anxiety, depression, stress, stress management, and ADHD. We meticulously crafted these question sets by consulting numerous research papers in the field of mental health. Each question in the sets presents the user with four options, each marked accordingly. Upon completing the questionnaire, users receive a report via email containing a brief overview of their current mental health status, along with guidance on understanding their condition. Additionally, we provide users with redirect links to our personalized chatbot and a website where they can locate nearby therapists for further assistance.

F. Chatbot

Chatbot is a software application created to mimic human conversation, typically via text or voice interfaces. Utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP), these programs interpret user input and generate responses accordingly. Chatbots can be programmed to carry out a range of tasks, including answering questions and offering information. Guiding users through processes, or even engaging in casual conversation. Overall, chatbots aim to deliver efficient and effective user interactions, frequently providing round-the-clock availability and scalability for businesses and organizations. So, we converted Mello-GPT into a portable Chatbot.

G. Working of our chatbot with the use of LLM?

After selecting Mello-GPT as our LLM and training it with our custom datasets, we achieved success in developing our personalized Chatbot. However, to ensure its accessibility to all users, we employed ReactJS to build a tailored website for the Chatbot's public use.

Drawbacks:

1. Large Files

The drawback of large files is that it increases storage space. Storing large files consumes more disk space, which can become a significant concern.

2. Requires Internet

The drawback of chatbots is it require an internet connection. If a user does not have access to the internet or if there are connectivity issues, they may not be able to interact with the chatbot.

3. Not Device Friendly

The drawback of chatbots is that they are not device-friendly for users who rely on specific devices or platforms. If a chatbot is not optimized for various devices such as smartphones, tablets, it may result in a bad user experience user.

4. Not Cost Efficient

Maintaining a sophisticated chatbot system can involve significant upfront costs and ongoing expenses. Initial development may require investment in skilled developers, AI technologies, and integration with existing systems.

Architecture Diagram

Figure 1: Architecture Diagram of our website and chatbot Mindflow

IV. RESULTS

Figure 2: Home Page of Mindflow website

Figure 3: Assessment Page of Mindflow website

Figure 4: Questionnaire on Mindflow website

Figure 5: Home page of Mindflow Chatbot

Figure 6: Login page of Mindflow Chatbot

Figure 7: Working of Mindflow Chatbot

V. COPYRIGHT AND LICENSES

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VI. CONCLUSION

By integrating ML and NLP to develop a mental health chatbot marked a significant advancement in delivering accessible and personalized care. By leveraging a powerful Language Model Mello-GPT, our chatbot can accurately and empathetically understand and respond to user inputs. Additionally, incorporating a well-crafted questionnaire to assess mental health allowed for tailored recommendations and interventions, enhancing the effectiveness of the support to be provided. This innovative approach not only expands access to mental health resources but also ensures a more responsive and user-focused experience, ultimately leading to improved mental health outcomes. Thus, we were able to provide a small yet somewhat effective solution to a underlying problem of Mental Health.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Miner, L. Miner, M. Goldstein et al., *Practical Predictive Analytics and Decisioning Systems for Medicine: Informatics Accuracy and Cost-Effectiveness for Healthcare Administration and Delivery Including Medical Research*, Academic Press, Inc., Cambridge, MA, USA, 1st edition, 2016.
- [2] M. Hamilton, "Development of a rating scale for primary depressive illness," *British Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 278–296, 1967.
- [3] American Psychiatric Association, *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, American Psychiatric Association, Reston, VA, USA, 2013.
- [4] M. I. Jordan and T. M. Mitchell, "Machine learning: trends, perspectives, and prospects," *Science*, vol. 349, no. 6245, pp. 255–260, 2011.
- [5] F. Dabek and J. J. Caban, "A neural network-based model for predicting psychological conditions," in *Brain Informatics and Health*, pp. 252–261, Springer International Publishing, Berlin, Germany, 2015.
- [6] G. Cho, J. Yim, Y. Choi, J. Ko, and S.-H. Lee, "Review of machine learning algorithms for diagnosing mental illness," *Psychiatry Investigation*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 262–269, 2019.
- [7] E. G. Pintelas, T. Kotsilieris, I. E. Livieris, and P. Pintelas, "A review of machine learning prediction methods for anxiety disorders," in *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Software Development and Technologies for Enhancing Accessibility and Fighting Info-Exclusion—DSAI 2018*, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2018.
- [8] R. B. Rutledge, A. M. Chekroud, and Q. J. Huys, "Machine learning and big data in psychiatry: toward clinical applications," *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, vol. 55, pp. 152–159, 2019.
- [9] Anu Priya, Shruti Garg, Neha Prerna Tigga, "Predicting Anxiety, Depression and Stress in Modern Life using Machine Learning Algorithms" in *International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Data Science (ICCIDS 2019)*, 2020
- [10] Astha Singh, Divya Kumar" *Identification of Anxiety and Depression Using DASS-21 Questionnaire and Machine Learning*" 2021 First International Conference on Advances in Computing and Future Communication Technologies
- [11] G. Parimala, R. Kayalvizhi, S. Nithiya "Mental Health: Detection & Diagnosis" Published in: 2022 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics
- [12] Saleh Afzoon, Nabi Rezvani, Farshad Khunjush "Enabling the Analysis of Mental Health Patterns Using an Efficient Machine Learning Approach" Published in: 2021 IEEE 25th International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Workshop
- [13] Reuben Crasto, Lance Dias, Dominic Miranda, Deepali Kayande" *CareBot: A Mental Health ChatBot*" Published in: 2021 2nd International Conference for Emerging Technology
- [14] Vivek More, Viren Koli, Vignesh Vijaykumar, Vimal Jethani" *Chatbot for mental well begin*"
- [15] Israt Jahan Dristy, Abdullah Matin Saad, Annajiat Alim Rasel" *Mental Health Status Prediction Using ML Classifiers with NLP-Based Approaches*" Published in: 2022 International Conference on Recent Progresses in Science, Engineering and Technology
- [16] 2023 Israt Jahan Dristy, Abdullah Matin Saad, Annajiat Alim Rasel proposed a paper on "Mental Health Status Prediction Using ML Classifiers with NLP Based Approaches" which provide the mental health status of the person by making use of ML classifiers and NLP approaches
- [17] In 2001 K Kroenke 1, R L Spitzer, J B Williams" *The PHQ-9: validity of a brief depression severity measure*" has focused on improving the detection of depression, assessment of severity is also important in guiding treatment decisions
- [18] Robert L Spitzer 1, Kurt Kroenke, Janet B W Williams, Bernd Löwe" *A brief measure for assessing generalized anxiety disorder: the GAD-7*" A brief measure for assessing generalized anxiety disorder: the GAD-7 Generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) is one of the most common mental disorders.
- [19] Ronald C Kessler 1, Lenard Adler, Minnie Ames, Olga Demler, Steve Faraone, Eva Hiripi, Mary J Howes, Robert Jin, Kristina Secnik, Thomas Spencer, T Bedirhan Ustun, Ellen E Walters" *The World Health Organization Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale (ASRS): a short screening scale for use in the general population*" includes 18 questions about frequency of recent DSM-IV Criterion A symptoms of adult ADHD. The ASRS screener consists of six out of these 18 questions that were selected based on stepwise logistic regression
- [20] Annabel Prins, PhD, Michelle J. Bovin, PhD, Derek J. Smolenski, PhD, MPH,5 Brian P. Marx, PhD, Rachel Kimerling, PhD, Michael A. Jenkins-Guarnieri, PhD, Danny G. Kaloupek, PhD, Paula P. Schnurr, PhD, Anica Pless Kaiser, PhD, Yani E. Leyva, PhD, and Quyen Q. Tiet," *The Primary Care PTSD Screen for DSM-5 (PC-PTSD-5): Development and Evaluation Within a Veteran Primary Care Sample*" The objective of this study was to revise the Primary Care PTSD screen (PC-PTSD) to reflect the new Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5)